

VILLAGE-BASED FLOOD PREDICTION WITH WATERVERSE - LOCALISING DIGITALISATION TO EMPOWER THE RESIDENTS OF ETTELN

Gareth Lewis¹, Barry Evans¹, Lydia Vamvakeridou-Lyroudia^{1,2},
Albert Chen¹, Slobodan Djordjević¹, Dragan Savić¹

¹Centre for Water Systems, University of Exeter, Exeter, EX1 2LU

²KWR Water Research Institute, Nieuwegein, 3433 PE.

¹g.lewis2@exeter.ac.uk

Keywords: flood prediction, FIWARE, citizen empowerment

ABSTRACT

We live in a time of increasing weather unpredictability. Weather events are becoming both more extreme and more frequent. In our area of expertise, flooding, we're increasingly talking to regions and towns that used to have grainy black and white photos of a single extreme flood from the last 50 years to now having videos of the last bad flood of the season.

Whilst weather prediction and associated flood prediction technologies have improved greatly, they still tend to operate on a macro-spatial level, providing broad warnings for relatively large areas. Conversely, the University of Exeter's (UNEXE) 'CA Flood Pro' application [1] has been developed to provide highly detailed, on a street-by-street basis, flooding simulations, but they are time consuming to run. For communities at risk of flooding, accuracy and timeliness of prediction are key. Therefore, for a CA Flood Pro based flooding simulation to be of value, it must provide quality predictions quickly.

The WATERVERSE [2] project has given us the opportunity to integrate CA Flood Pro flood prediction application into the Water Data Management Ecosystem (WDME), along with sources of historic, current, and predicted precipitation, and ground condition data, to provide Etteln, a small town in Germany, with highly localised and up-to-date flood predictions.

INTRODUCTION

The WATERVERSE project [2] is an EU-funded project aimed at developing a Water Data Management Ecosystem (WDME) for making data management practices and resources in the water sector accessible, affordable, secure, fair, and easy to use, and engaged with six European water companies to embed the WDME with their processes. The WDME seeks to ingest and harmonise data from a variety of sources allowing it to be viewed and processed with the WDME's component-based architecture, Figure 1, the philosophies being that re-usable components can be deployed across a number of pilots and the visual plug-and-play approach of the WDME's mash-up editor empowers non-technical users to define and process dataflows and associated transformations, Figure 2.

Etteln is a village in the German State of North Rhine-Westphalia and sits in the river Altenau valley. Historically, the valley and Etteln have been subject to flooding due to rainfall and associated river overflow. As a 'digital lighthouse

village' [3], the village has installed a large array of sensors, including rainfall, and now collects, processes and visualises data for the villagers.

To leverage this data for flood prediction, Etteln has become a partner in the WATERVERSE project, with its local data added to the WDME and UNEXE has provided its CA Flood application to simulate flood events based on both historic data from Etteln's sensors and forecast data provided by HST Systemtechnik.

Figure 1 - WDME logical architecture

Figure 2 - Mash-up editor in WDME

METHOD

The Etteln flood prediction component was developed for the WDME as a Django webservice with a POST request that would enable clients to send historic and predicted rainfall data in order to run flood simulations and a set of GET requests that would enable flood prediction results to be collected as regional flood images, geojson flood models, and quantitative reports for the Etteln website.

To model the Etteln region, four geospatial files were constructed: an elevation model, an infiltration model to describe the land surface's ability to absorb rainfall, a surface roughness model, and rainfall catchment model showing the range of each sensor, Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Etteln flood prediction dataset: DEM (left), land classification (centre), and rainfall catchments (right).

The overall flood prediction process was split into three distinct parts: 1) ‘current’ flood conditions using historic data over the last 72 hours (3 days), a ‘nowcast’ using predictions over the next 2 hours, and a longer-range forecast of 72 hours, Figure 4, providing a six day window of analysis and prediction.

Figure 4 – flood prediction process

By running 3 small predictions rather than one large one, we could use the ‘peak’ output file for each micro-prediction, showing the worst / deepest flooding over the period and present that data to the user. We found this approach to be of great use from our work on flooding digital twins [4] on the ARSINOE project [5], in so far as whilst flooding events may be quite short (in terms of actual rainfall), the soak-away time of the resulting flooding tends to be longer term, or at least within the 72 hour windows presented.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The flood prediction component was initially developed as a Windows-based bench test application before being ported to Linux and refactored into a Django-based web service to interface with the WDME infrastructure. As part of this initial work, we developed a simple Mapbox-based website that would be fed flooding output data (as geojson file) for geospatial visualisation. This was later developed into a ‘proper’ visualisation as part of the Django server.

During development we made significant use of synthetic data generation [6], given the relative lack of heavy rainfall in the Etteln region. This allowed us to explore very specific weather events (historic flooding, heavy rainfall during the nowcast period, heavy rainfall in the early, mid and late forecast periods and so on) to test and validate the operation and output of the flood prediction component. Figure 5 details three synthetic traces over time using HST’s epoch driven approach, rather than time series.

Figure 5 - Synthetic rainfall models over time

High tail

This model depicts historic long-term rainfall, with a period of dryness followed by a forecast of heavy rain at the end of the forecast period, around 300mm over 24hrs (about 12mm per hour). Figure 6 shows some historic flooding in the current rainfall simulation (left) whilst the forecast rainfall (right) shows increased flooding around the village centre and southern parts.

Figure 6 - High tail simulation showing current rainfall (left) and forecast rainfall (right)

Forecast short burst

This model depicts an intense period of rainfall (25mm per hour) over a short period (2 hours). The impact on the village is clear, Figure 7, showing substantial flooding around the centre of the village (left) and the valley floors around the village. However, by the end of the simulation period + 72hrs, the flood has largely receded.

Figure 7 - Short burst simulation showing result of intense rainfall (left) and recovery by end of simulation period (right)

Historic rainfall

This model depicts prolonged, but fairly light, rainfall over the past two and a half days (72 hours to 12 hours). Figure 8 shows some flooding around the village centre in the current simulation (left), whilst the end of the forecast simulation shows a largely dry centre (right).

Figure 8 - Historic rainfall showing some flooding in the current simulation (left), before drying out by the end of the forecast simulation

CONCLUSIONS

As a part of the WDME, the flood prediction component has worked well, being able to collect and process relatively arbitrary weather data and produce simulation results that make sense. Although the simulation can take some time to run (c1-2minutes) the results have temporal value and separating the POST / GET functions allows the component to work within the WDME architecture.

The source data provided for flood simulation has provided challenging as it necessary to convert it to time series for flood prediction and, moreover, the long periods presented can limit the value of prediction, particularly in cases where there is a short but intense rainfall that results in flash flooding. Likewise, CA Flood currently has limited modelling provision for rivers and no support for wastewater systems, so the results for Etteln are likely to be worse than real-world results. However, work is underway to provide SWMM [7] integration.

For UNEXE, the key lessons learnt from this project have been in the innovations of flood simulation by, ironically, scaling down digitisation. By reducing the complexity of simulation inputs, simulation response times have improved greatly, allowing CA Flood Pro to be both considered and used in more time sensitive areas of simulation.

Likewise, working within the WDME framework, we have been able to concentrate on the most important parts of flood simulation. By taking a block-based approach to WDME component development, users are empowered to create their own data processing flows without handing so much work off to experts. This also gives us the opportunity to 'lift and shift' the flood simulation model off to other pilots, given the generic processing nature of the WDME.

Finally, developing flooding output visualisations with the Etteln users has allowed us to build a sense of trust, as the visualisations are presented in a manner and format that makes sense to the users. Moving forward, we can co-develop the output process beyond purely web-based visualisation to provide solutions that make sense to the users and will provide value in stressful times.

The work presented in this paper was funded by the ongoing EC H2020 Waterverse (GA 101070262) project.

REFERENCES

- [1] University of Exeter, "CAFlood Pro Homepage," [Online]. Available: <https://cafloodpro.com/>. [Accessed 10 February 2025].
- [2] EU, "WATERVERSE Homepage," [Online]. Available: <https://waterverse.eu/>. [Accessed 10 february 2025].
- [3] FIWARE, "Etteln: Digital Lighthouse Village," [Online]. Available: <https://www.fiware.org/2025/04/04/etteln-digital-lighthouse-village/>. [Accessed 30 March 2025].
- [4] G. Lewis, M. Khoury, Q. Li, B. Evans, A. S. Chen, S. Djordjevic, L. S. Vamvakeridou-Lyroudia, D. A. Savic and N. Mustafee, "CREATING AND OPERATING A SIMULATION-BASED DIGITAL TWIN SERVICE FOR HYDROLOGIC FLOOD," in *Proceedings of the Operational Research Society Simulation Workshop 2025 (SW25)*, Exeter, 2025.
- [5] ARSINOE, "The ARSINOE project," [Online]. Available: <https://arsinoe-project.eu/>. [Accessed 30 March 2025].
- [6] G.Lewis, S.Seshan, E. d. Vos, L.Vamvakeridou-Lyroudia, A.Chen, S.Djordjević and D. A. Savić, "Building a WDME-centric synthetic data infrastructure for the WATERVERSE project," in *Proceedings of The 4th International Joint Conference on Water Distribution Systems Analysis & Computing and Control for the Water Industry (WDSA/CCWI 2025)*, Sheffield, 2025.
- [7] EPA, "Storm Water Management Model (SWMM)," [Online]. Available: <https://www.epa.gov/water-research/storm-water-management-model-swmm>. [Accessed 30 March 2025].